

The variables affecting the willingness to be flexible in exchange for financial compensation of consumers by smart heat pump usage to support the smart grid.

Research Academic competences Group 4

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Abstract:

This study aims to identify factors influencing the acceptance of flexible heat pumps that support smart grid systems. The study is based on journal research, interviews and questionnaires to determine what variables affect heat pump users' willingness to give up comfort in exchange for energy tariff discounts. The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) Theory is used and adapted to create a conceptual model including the found variables affecting the perceived usefulness of flexible heat pump usage. Five semi-structured interviews are conducted among central heating experts with practical or theoretical work experience. The most important factors influencing the willingness to be flexible amongst heat pump users are their financial situation and their perceived usefulness of the smart grid. To test the impact of these variables, 385 questionnaires are handed out to homeowners. In total, 78,1% of the participants are "likely" to "highly likely" to offer flexibility in exchange for financial compensation by smart heat pump usage.

Keywords: Smart grid, Smart heat pumps, TAM, Compensation, Consumer flexibility

Introduction

The Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022 caused a worldwide energy crisis. It highlighted the vulnerability of the global energy market to geopolitical and economic disruptions (IEA, 2022). In combination with the growing awareness of the effects of global warming amongst society and policymakers. Countries such as the Netherlands realized the emergence of a fast energy transition (Können, 2022). Therefore, the demand and production of renewable energy are rising (Gielen et al., 2019). Two trillion euros will be invested globally in renewable energy sources between now and the year 2030 (IEA, 2022). In the Netherlands, 33% of the electricity produced is renewable (Können, 2022). It is expected that by 2030, almost all electricity will be renewable in the Netherlands (ter Voorde 2022).

One of the disadvantages of renewable energy sources is the fluctuations in supply caused by weather conditions (Gielen et al., 2019). These fluctuations can lead to temporary energy shortages or surpluses based on the balance between supply and demand. The supply uncertainty will enhance the need for flexibility to avoid imbalances in the power system (Kubli et al., 2018). A solution to this problem is the emergence of smart grids. A *smart grid* is an electricity distribution network that uses digital communication technology to adapt to electricity demand and store energy based on the available supply. This stored energy can later be used when there is an energy shortage (Shomali & Pinkse, 2016).

Presently smart grid technology has yet to be implemented in the Netherlands, and the current energy grid needs to undergo a digital transformation before it is ready to be used. In order to realize this, electrical devices can be connected to an Internet Of Things (IoT) device, which makes it possible to communicate with the smart grid (Wang et al., 2017). The IoT device extracts data from the central system about the current electricity balance between demand and supply. Based on this balance, the device can decide whether to consume and store energy. This method has a fast response rate and can be automated, which makes it suitable for balancing the power grid (Brooks et al., 2010). The system is called aggregated load control (Saleh et al., 2016).

One promising technology that can be connected to the smart grid by IoT is heat pumps. Heat pumps appeal because they have a high-performance coefficient (van Nuffel, 2018). Unlike conventional gas-consuming boilers, heat pumps make use of electricity. Heat pumps extract heat from the air, ground or groundwater and use this heat to warm a

building or store heated water in a buffer tank (Irena, 2019). Because of this, heat pumps can be part of the solution to reach the decarbonization goals. Worldwide 5% of all heating is realized by heat pumps. This number is expected to increase and triple in 2030 (IEA, 2022). This makes it highly useful for the smart grid in the future.

Smart heat pumps support the smart grid by heating the house or storing energy in the buffer tank only during an energy surplus. When an energy shortage occurs, the smart heat pump stops consuming electricity. However, the house can still be warmed with the heated water stored in the buffer tank. Once the energy shortage is over, the smart heat pump will fill up the buffer tank again (Gelazaskas, 2014). However, it can occur that the electricity shortage will take longer than a buffer tank can warm the house. When this occurs, the heat pump only warms the house to a limited temperature to lower the electricity consumption until the energy shortage ends. Consumers get financial compensation in exchange for the possible discomfort caused by a lower temperature. In this way, smart heat pumps can warm houses while supporting the smart grid (Kubli et al., 2018).

PROBLEM STATEMENT

One of the main problems is that consumers of smart heat pumps are not likely to offer flexibility to support smart grids (Kubli et al., 2018). It needs to be clarified what causes this unwillingness to offer flexibility. However, it is found that electricity firms are likely to only invest in smart grids if customer engagement is high (Shomali et al., 2016). Despite this uncertainty, the emergence of a smart grid is rising, and the Dutch national electricity network needs to be prepared for the consequences of this sustainable energy transition. Once consumers are more willing to cooperate, electricity firms will be more likely to invest in the smart grid, and fewer fossil fuels will be needed in the future to absorb this energy fluctuation.

Literature review

The literature review has been conducted by analyzing the TAM model and Flexible energy usage and smart grids.

Technology Acceptance Model

TAM was developed in the late 1980s by Fred D. Davis. This model's goals were to understand better why users accept or reject technology and how design iterations could lead to higher user

acceptance. TAM is based on the theory of Reasoned Action from Fishbein and Ajzen (Ammenwerth, 2019).

The TAM model is widely adopted and considered a "gold standard" in technology acceptance (Ammenwerth, 2019). The foundation of the TAM model exists out of two beliefs whereby Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of use impact the attitude towards using. This attitude towards using, combined with Perceived Usefulness, impacts the Behavioral Intention To Use.

This study uses a part of the TAM model to inspire the conceptual model. This study aims to expand the existing literature on the TAM model with new variables specific to this situation.

Flexible energy usage and smart grids

In the past, much research has been conducted on flexible energy usage and smart grids. Experts agree on the significant potential of decentralized, flexible energy usage and storage, which is required for renewable energy sources (Helms et al., 2016). However, the infrastructure and IT infrastructure to support this system

are lacking (Kondziella & Bruckner, 2016). These changes will lead to a revolution in the energy market, and new business models are being developed and researched (Burger & Luke, 2017).

Energy companies are likely to refrain from engaging in this new business model as long as it is unclear whether consumers are willing to cooperate (Shomali & Pinkse, 2016). Where Kubli et al. (2018) researched that prosumers with electric car batteries and solar PV batteries are more likely to offer flexibility than prosumers with heat pumps. This means that prosumers are likelier to give a percentage of their electric car battery than give up a few degrees Celsius in their home temperature, even if this has high financial benefits.

While (van Heuveln et al., 2021) researched what variables cause the (un) willingness to cooperate with the smart grid by offering electrical car battery capacity. No research has been done regarding variables affecting the willingness to cooperate in flexible heat pump usage.

RESEARCH QUESTION

This paper aims to explore what variables play a role and how much impact they have on the acceptance of flexible heat pump usage. To answer this question, the following questions are sought.

Main question

What variables significantly impact the acceptance of flexible smart heat pump usage of consumers to support the smart grid?

Sub questions

What variables have a significant impact on the perceived usefulness of the smart grid?

What variables significantly impact the willingness to offer flexible heat pump usage (intention to use)?

Is there a correlation between the perceived usefulness of the smart grid and the willingness to offer flexible heat pump usage (intention to use)?

These sub-questions are incorporated into the hypothesis and the conceptual model.

Methodology

Research objective

To answer the main question, "What variables have a significant impact on the acceptance of flexible smart heat pump usage of consumers to support the smart grid?" qualitative empirical research will be conducted. This descriptive research aims to gain insight into the multiple concepts that might influence acceptance, like financial situation, sustainability awareness and reward in exchange for discomfort. The influence of these concepts on the intention to use could be relevant for future projects and research. It will offer a deeper understanding of the acceptance of technology with a flexibility option.

Research design

Both primary and secondary data will be used for this study. The primary data will be collected using semi-structured interviews and cross-sectional surveys. Semi-structured interviews are used because this is an effective method to collect qualitative data about possible variables affecting the research. After this qualitative data is collected, the survey strategy was chosen because it is broadly applicable, accessible for respondents to understand and suitable for soliciting opinions and statements (Wieringa, 2014, pp. 45-46). The secondary data will consist of academic literature and will be used to supplement and ensure the reliability of the primary data.

The primary data collection method was established through the 'research onion model' (Saunders & Lewis, 2017, pp. 104-136). Since the research question and objectives are decisive, the research will be pragmatic. The smart grid heat pump concept is relatively new and has yet to be implemented. A small amount of data or theories on smart grids exists; therefore, the research will be inductive. This article aims to expand on existing theories to show the impact of flexibility on the acceptance of smart grid technology.

Population and sampling method

The sampling frame will consist of the number of households in the Netherlands. This will focus on those who pay energy bills. This is because these people can make the most reliable assumption of to what extent they are willing to sacrifice comfort in return for a reward. Other household members are less relevant to this study because they are not responsible for the bill and, therefore, cannot make a reliable trade-off between comfort and reward. The sample size was calculated to ensure that those in the sample represent the population. The number of households in the Netherlands is about 8.1 million. Therefore, the T-value of 'infinity' respondents is used in the sample calculation (Centraal Bureau Voor de Statistiek, 2022). Using a confidence interval of 95% with an accuracy margin of 50% and a 5% error margin, it is concluded that the sample should have at least 385 respondents.

Data collection methods

The purpose of the data collection methods is to calculate what correlation "giving up comfort" against "fee contributes" to the acceptance of smart grid technology.

Due to the lack of time and budget and the unavailability of a representative sampling frame, the data collection methods will consist of the non-probability sampling technique: convenience sampling, as the researchers need to learn the contact details of people with smart heat systems. The researchers cannot request this information from a database for privacy reasons. That is why the samples were conducted in the researchers' networks. This also applies to the exploratory semi-structured interviews.

Convenient sampling has the risk of being less generalizable. However, by surveying a large enough sample, this risk is found to be irrelevant. Internal validity and reliability will be further ensured by consistently using the same survey,

using multi-item and single-item scales to measure the abstract attribute 'flexibility', using multiple researchers and statistically testing the survey results with Cronbach's Alpha. The sample was drawn from all researchers' networks to increase the study's external validity. This ensured that people from different environments completed the survey, and it is more likely that consumers from multiple walks of life met the study.

Measure instrument and data collection

The survey questions were prepared using a five-point Likert scale. The questions are in the form of statements that respondents can evaluate using a five-point Likert scale going from 'strongly disagree' to 'strongly agree'. The questions were created based on literature research and interviews with experts. To test whether the survey would be precise for respondents, a sample survey was first sent to several respondents and asked how they interpreted the questions. The feedback provided was incorporated to ensure that the survey would be apparent to all respondents. The results of the test surveys were not used as data for the study. Aside from preventing bias from the researchers, several measures were taken to prevent bias from the respondent. To avoid a non-response bias as much as possible, the survey was kept short and communicated to the respondents. Also, several methods were used to deploy the survey: e-mail and WhatsApp links. To make people complete the survey as honestly as possible, respondents have been stressed that the survey is entirely anonymous. This must also prevent social desirability bias. To avoid question-order bias. The survey questions have been divided into groups, and in this group, the questions are in random order. The researchers also know that respondents may need to become more familiar with the smart Grid's concept. To avoid information bias, the survey explained the smart grid idea and the terms used (Saunders & Lewis, 2017, pp. 137-170).

Collecting and analyzing data

The data collection took place between 31 October 2022 and 7 November 2022. Due to time limitations, the survey was only sent to about 120 people, of which 55 responded. This is a response rate of almost 46%. Meaning the target number of 385 respondents still needs to be met. The 55 responses were used in the completion of the research.

To analyze the data, the program IBM SPSS Statistics was used. Since multiple independent

variables exist and the ordinal scale in questions consists of intervals from 1 to 5, the relationships will be analyzed using regression analysis.

Figure 1: Conceptual model

Hypotheses

The conceptual model shows the relationships between the multiple concepts used in this study. Most of the concepts represented in the conceptual model are from the TAM model, except for Financial situation, Sustainability awareness and Reward/discomfort (Ammenwerth, 2019).

Sustainability awareness shows the height of a respondent's awareness of the consumer's impact on the environment. The financial situation is based on five levels representing the impact high prices have on the respondent, with level 5 meaning that high prices have a strong influence. Furthermore, lastly, the reward/discomfort; this concept shows how flexible respondents are when posed with a question that gives a financial reward in exchange for a lower comfort in their home (lower temperature inside).

Based on the relationships between these concepts, the following hypotheses are drawn up:

- H1: A healthy financial situation of a person positively affects sustainability awareness.
- H2: A poor financial situation of a person has a positive effect on the willingness to trade off discomfort in exchange for financial compensation.
- H3: A person's sustainability awareness positively affects the perceived usefulness of Smart grid solutions.
- H4: A person that is willing to trade discomfort in exchange for financial compensation will be more likely to have the intention to use a smart heat pump.
- H5: A higher perceived usefulness will lead to a higher intention to use flexible smart heat pumps.

Data analyses & Results

An explorative interview was conducted to collect data for the survey's design. Based on the interview results, a questionnaire was composed with the variables: financial situation, sustainability awareness, reward/discomfort level, perceived usefulness, intention to use and smart grid acceptance. The most significant variables from the interview are that wealthier people are generally less frugal with their energy consumption. Meanwhile, most people invest in sustainability measures to save money on their energy bills. Another incentive mentioned during the interview is that people want to contribute to climate protection. With the current unstable energy market, consumers are becoming much more energy conscious, according to the expert, and the expert sees more and more consumers taking measures to make their homes more energy neutral. People with solar panels are already storing energy in buffer vessels when their solar panels generate more energy than they consume.

After analyzing the data from the survey using SPSS, the following results were observed. Starting with Cronbach's Alpha (Tabel 1) to show the internal reliability of the financial situation variable as this is the only multi-item variable. A high Cronbach's Alpha is necessary for a reliable hypothesis test. The generally accepted rule is that a Cronbach's Alpha between 0.6 and 0.7 is acceptable and from 0.8 is good. As shown in Table 1, Cronbach's Alpha is 0.675. This means that the reliability of the results is acceptable (Ursachi & Horodnic, 2015).

Table 1: Calculated Cronbach's Alpha for research variable

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha
Financial situation	0.674

Note. Calculated with SPSS.

Regression analysis was used to test H1, which states that a person's financial situation positively affects sustainability awareness. No significant positive effect of the financial situation on sustainability awareness was found, thus rejecting H1 ($F(1.53) = .430, p = .515$) $r = 0.090$.

Regression analysis shows that a significant positive effect was found between a person's financial situation and the willingness to trade off comfort in exchange for financial compensation ($F(1.53) = 6.049, p = .017$), meaning H2 is accepted with a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.320$.

Using regression analysis hypothesis 3, The sustainability awareness of a person has a positive effect on the perceived usefulness of the smart grid was tested. No significant positive effect was found, meaning a rejection of H3($F(1.53) = 1.588$, $p = 0.213$) $r = 0.171$.

Linear regression analysis shows a significant positive effect between the willingness to trade off discomfort in exchange for financial compensation and intention to use ($F(1.53) = 14.266$, $p = <.001$), meaning H4 is accepted with a correlation coefficient of $r = 0.461$.

Finally, H5, A higher perceived usefulness will lead to a higher intention to use flexible smart heat pumps, is tested using linear regression analysis and shows a significant positive effect of perceived usefulness on intention to use ($F(1.53) = 18.501$, $p = <.001$) meaning H5 is accepted with a correlation coefficient of

$r = 0.509$.

The variables reward/discomfort and perceived usefulness play, with a correlation between 0.3 and 0.5, an essential role in the acceptance of SMART grid systems. Because the analysis showed sufficient evidence to adopt H2, H4 and H5, this study has shown that a person willing to trade inconvenience for financial compensation will be more likely to use a smart heat pump. Also, a person's financial situation positively affects the willingness to trade off discomfort in exchange for financial compensation.

In addition, H1 and H3 were not used because the significance values were too high. As a result, there was a high chance that the hypotheses would be wrongly adopted, as a 95% confidence value was used, and the values from the mentioned hypotheses were above this value.

Figure 2: correlations in the conceptual model.

Discussion

The growing amount of renewable energy sources requires a smart grid. A part of the smart grid is smart heat pumps. However, what drives consumers to use smart heat pumps still needs to be determined. As long as consumers' engagement is low or unclear, energy companies are not likely to engage in smart grids. This will most likely lead to a national energy distribution problem in the future.

While previous studies only focused on whether people are willing to offer flexibility. Our study added variables that impact the willingness to collaborate. To do this, the TAM model was used, and it was found that the TAM model is also helpful for flexible smart heat pump usage in exchange for financial compensation. It is found that if consumers have higher perceived usefulness of smart grids, they are more likely to have the intention to use smart heat pumps. Besides, it is added that if people are less wealthy, they are more likely to have the intention to use Smart heat pumps. The last variable that was coupled to the TAM model is sustainability awareness and whether that has an impact on the perceived usefulness. However, this relationship seems weak.

When comparing our results with previous research, one of the most remarkable observations is that there was a significant positive relationship between the willingness to offer flexibility in exchange for financial compensation and the intention to use smart heat pumps. The rising energy prices and inflation in the Netherlands in 2022 could cause this change in willingness to collaborate. While the research of Kubli states that prosumers of smart heat pumps are not likely to trade off discomfort in exchange for financial compensation.

Because consumers with higher perceived usefulness of smart grid are more likely to have the intention to use smart heat pumps, it could be helpful to set up a national marketing campaign to inform consumers about the importance of supporting the smart grid. In this way, people are more likely to understand the importance of the smart grid and therefore are more likely to engage in smart heat pump usage. During the implementation of the smart grid, it is recommended to focus on less wealthy consumers because they are more likely to use a smart heat pump in exchange for financial compensation. This is likely because they feel the consequences of inflation the most. However, the problem is that less wealthy people are less likely to purchase a smart heat pump due to the investment. It emerged from the interview that buying a hybrid heat

pump can easily be around €5000. A solution to this problem could be subsidising smart heat pumps for less wealthy people. This way, these consumers can invest in a smart heat pump and support the smart grid system.

Further research could focus on simulating a situation where consumers use smart heat pumps. To do this, a pattern must be simulated, representing natural fluctuations in energy supply caused by renewable energy. This pattern could then be connected to the smart heat pump. The smart heat pump can then react to these fluctuations, and in this way, a situation can be simulated where the smart grid is running. By using these simulations, consumers can experience flexible heat pump consumption. This will better represent how consumers will experience smart heat pump consumption. Furthermore, therefore give more realistic results of how much discomfort consumers are willing to trade in exchange for financial compensation.

Another suggestion for future research is whether consumers are willing to trade discomfort in exchange for financial compensation with technologies that also support smart grids or other systems that could benefit society. Research in this area could prove the generalisation of our variables on the TAM model.

Future research is suggested to research the factors influencing the reward/discomfort level. Since this paper only shows a moderate effect of the financial situation on the reward/discomfort level.

The last thing that should be considered is that the research was done during an energy crisis. Therefore people are more aware of their energy consumption. The results would differ once the energy crisis is over. Therefore it is recommended that when the energy crisis ends. The research could be done again to figure out whether the impact differs.

Conclusion

This study shows a significant positive relationship between a difficult financial situation of a person to the willingness to be flexible. This relationship shows that less wealthy consumers are willing to sacrifice more for a reward. No significant effect was found between financial situation and sustainability awareness, meaning that the wealthier are not necessarily more focused on sustainability. Besides, sustainability is not significantly influencing the perceived usefulness. Overall, a consumer's willingness to trade off comfort for a

reward/discount (flexibility) plays a substantial role in the intention to use smart heat pumps. At the same time, the financial situation moderately impacts the willingness to trade discomfort for a reward.

This addition to the traditional TAM model is recommended to take into account in other research where discomfort in exchange for a reward plays a role.

There are multiple limitations in the sample of this research. One limitation is that the research group could only interview one expert on heat pumps. More interviews would lead to more variables that could affect the willingness of consumers and could further stress the importance of the chosen variables. Therefore it is unclear whether these variables are the most important variables affecting the perceived usefulness and intention to use. However, it is found that these variables impact the TAM model through the surveys. However, not all relations could be proven significant. This is because only 55 people responded to the survey. While the goal was to have 385 respondents to ensure all correlations were relevant. However, some correlations are still significant.

The last limitation regarding the sample is the way the sample was selected. The survey was handed out to direct contacts of the researchers. Because of this, a self-selection bias could occur. Therefore, the sample may not give a realistic representation of the Dutch population and might not be generalizable.

Besides the limitation in the research sample, one of the main limitations is that the smart grid currently does not exist. Therefore the research is limited to an interview and questionnaire. This questionnaire could test what people expect to be willing to trade-off. However, in real life, it could be that people over- or underestimate how much discomfort they think is acceptable for their expected financial compensation. Nevertheless, this research does give a first indication of how much people are likely to collaborate.

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